

of chair form in the ligand were located at 1 075 and 1 135 cm^{-1} and these remained unaltered in complexes, indicating the coordination of complexes in the chair form. The dithiocyanato complex displayed $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ at 2 100 cm^{-1} as sharp and strong band, while $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ at 710 cm^{-1} and δ_{NCS} at 490 cm^{-1} fall in the range of S bonded thiocyanate group^{12, 13}. The splitting of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band could not be observed in $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{SCN})_2]$ suggesting *trans*-bonding of SCN groups. The dinitro complex $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ displays $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1 430 cm^{-1} as well as $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{NO}_2)$ at 1 375 cm^{-1} as strong and broad bands and δ_{ONO} at 820 cm^{-1} . The ir frequencies of NO_2 group were observed in the range of N-bonded nitro groups^{13, 14}. The absence of splitting of δ_{ONO} and $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{NO}_2)$ vibrations also suggested *trans*-bonding of nitro group in $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2]$. The ir bands of the cream yellow and greenish yellow $[\text{PdL}_2\text{Br}_2]$ complexes differed appreciably in the far-ir region. The greenish yellow variety displayed six bands in the far-ir regions at 485s, 455s, 360s, 310w, 265s and 240s cm^{-1} while the cream-yellow variety displayed only four bands at 480m, 360s, 265w and 240w cm^{-1} . The occurrence of more bands in greenish complex indicated *cis*-arrangement of the ligand molecules around palladium(II)¹⁵. The new ir bands in the region 500–240 cm^{-1} of the complexes were presumably due to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{X}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$ vibrations¹⁶.

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Heterogeneous Coated Wire Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) Ion Selective Electrodes based on Solid Ion-Exchange Resin

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THE present paper describes the use of a coated wire electrode in which a liquid ion-exchanger has been replaced by a solid ion-exchange resin. Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} ion-sensitive electrode were prepared using the metal form of a solid cation-exchange resin as the electroactive material and silicone rubber as the inert binder. Nernstian response, response time, effect of pH, working range, and selectivity coefficient have been evaluated.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade and all the solutions prepared in double-distilled water. Solid cation-exchange resin (Dowex 50W-4) was treated with saturated solutions of metal chlorides through the column to obtain its metal forms. One part of the metal form of the cation-exchange resin was mixed with four parts of silicone rubber (Sylartivi-11, Metroark) to make a homogeneous paste and a few drops of catalyst which was supplied by the manufacturer (Metroark) along with the silicone rubber, were added to it. A small portion of the paste thus formed was coated on one end of the copper wire attached to central conductor of coaxial cable; care was taken to form a small bead at the tip of the wire. It was dried in air and treated with 0.1 M metal(II) solution.

A Philips PR 9405 M pH meter was used for the potential measurements with a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. The electrodes were pretreated with solutions of metal(II) ions before measurements.

Results and Discussion

The parameters, like Nernstian response, response time, pH dependence, working range, selectivity coefficient and life time have been evaluated¹ for both Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} sensitive coated wire electrodes. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELECTRODES

Parameters	Cu ²⁺ - sensitive electrode	Co ²⁺ - sensitive electrode
Nernstian response		
Slope (mV/p)	30	35
Working range (M)	1 × 10 ⁻¹ - 1 × 10 ⁻⁴	1 × 10 ⁻¹ - 5 × 10 ⁻⁵
Working pH range	3-8	2-8
Response time (s)	60	45
Life-time (week)	8	10

In order to exploit the electrode systems for determining the metal(II) ion directly in the presence of other cations, the selectivity coefficients were calculated by mixed solution method² for each electrode. The potentials in mixed solution against a constant background of foreign ions *viz.* Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mg²⁺, Co²⁺ (or Cu²⁺) at different concentrations were measured and the selectivity coefficients for the electrodes were found to be 1.00, 0.77, 0.15, 0.25, 0.25 for the Cu²⁺ sensitive electrode, and 0.29, 0.15, 0.10, 0.50 and 0.48, respectively for the Co²⁺ sensitive electrode.

Nitroso-R-salt forms³ 1:1 and 1:2 complex with Co²⁺ in aqueous solution in the acidic range of pH. In order to test the suitability of these electrodes, the stability constant of both the species was determined, using Co²⁺ ion sensitive electrode. The log K₁ (6.78) and log K₂ (5.48) values thus obtained agree with the literature values^{4,5}.

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Laser Raman Spectroscopic Investigation of SF₄ Molecule†

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THE sulphur tetrafluoride molecule has a geometrical configuration belonging to C_{2v} point group. The present investigation is aimed at obtaining the complete laser Raman vibrational

spectrum of the SF₄ molecule and to perform a normal coordinate treatment to obtain a set of reasonable molecular constants. Dodd *et al*¹ have reported the first vibrational spectrum of SF₄. Subsequently, several investigators^{2,3} have reported vibrational spectrum of SF₄ in solid and gas phase. In the present investigation, the laser Raman spectrum of SF₄, its assignment and the vibrational analysis are reported.

Frequency assignment : Spectroscopically pure SF₄ gas has been obtained from the Division of Applied Chemistry, Madras Institute of Technology. The laser Raman spectrum of SF₄ was recorded using 488 nm line of Ar⁺ for excitation in the region 100-2 000 cm⁻¹ on a Cary 82 grating spectrophotometer using 4W argon laser. The observed frequencies along with the assignment are presented in Table 1. The molecule gives rise to nine fundamental vibrations classified as 4A₁+A₂+2B₁+2B₂ and all the vibrations are Raman active.

TABLE 1—MOLECULAR PARAMETERS AND WAVE NUMBERS OF OBSERVED FUNDAMENTALS OF SF₄ MOLECULE

Species	Designation	Wave numbers cm ⁻¹	Description
A ₁	ν ₁	892vs(p)	ν _g -SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₂	556vs(p)	ν _g -SF ₂ axial
	ν ₃	475m	δ _g cis-SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₄	228w	δ _g cis-SF ₂ axial
A ₂	ν ₅	412vw	δ-SF ₂ twist
B ₁	ν ₆	867m	ν _{as} -SF ₂ axial
	ν ₇	532s	δ rock
B ₂	ν ₈	734vw	ν _{as} -SF ₂ equatorial
	ν ₉	351vw	δ wag

Structural parameters : D = 1.646 Å, d = 1.545 Å, R = 0.54 Å, α = 101°33', β = 86°32', γ = 129°15', η = 93°28'.

vs(p) = very strong (polarised), s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, vw = very weak.

The bands at 892 and 556 cm⁻¹ are strongly polarised and hence they belong to A₁ species. They are assigned to ν₁-SF₂ symmetrical and ν₂-SF₂ axial vibrations. The band set 867 and 734 cm⁻¹ are assigned to asymmetric S-F₂ axial stretching vibration (ν₆) and asymmetric SF₂ equatorial stretching (ν₈), respectively. These observations clearly agree with the available infrared data for this molecule. The bands at 475 and 228 cm⁻¹ appear to be closely polarised and hence they are assigned to A₁ type vibration, *i.e.* 475 cm⁻¹ is assigned to δ *cis*-SF₂ equatorial while 228 cm⁻¹ is assigned to δ *cis*-SF₂ axial. The band at 532 cm⁻¹ is depolarised and it is assigned to δ-rock ν₇. The band at 351 cm⁻¹ is assigned to ν₉(B₂) from the previous data, on this molecule. The remaining fundamental SF₂ twisting mode is possible only in Raman spectrum and this frequency is assigned to 412 cm⁻¹. The present study agrees very well with the values reported in the literature for this molecule, especially with infrared spectrum

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